

Synthesis and properties of long chain carboxyl and dicarboxyl chelated ruthenium organometallics incorporating the imine-phenol motif

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The reaction of sodium palmitate (NaPm) and disodium terephthalate (Na_2Tp) with $\text{Ru}(\text{RL}^1)(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{CO})\text{Cl}$ (**1**) has respectively furnished $\text{Ru}(\text{RL}^2)(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{CO})(\text{Pm})$ (**2**) and $[\text{Ru}(\text{RL}^2)(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{CO})]_2(\text{Tp})$ (**3**) in excellent yield (RL^1 is $\text{C}_6\text{H}_2\text{O}-2\text{-CHNHC}_6\text{H}_4\text{R}(\text{p})-3\text{-Me}-5$, RL^2 is $\text{C}_6\text{H}_2\text{OH}-2\text{-CHNHC}_6\text{H}_4\text{R}(\text{p})-3\text{-Me}-5$ and R is Me, Cl). The chelation of palmitate/terephthalate is attended with the cleavage of Ru–O and Ru–Cl bonds and iminium-phenolato \rightarrow imine-phenol prototropic shift. In dichloromethane solution **2** and **3** display one and two quasireversible $\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}/\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}$ cyclic voltammetric response with $E_{1/2}$ near 0.6 V and 0.6 V, 0.9 V vs SCE due to the presence of one and two Ru^{II} centres respectively. Coulometrically generated solution of 2^+ and 3^+ are EPR-active due to the formation of trivalent ruthenium and mixed valent diruthenium organometallics.

The chemistry of new orthometallated ruthenium are of current interest in the context of synthesis^{1–3} and reactivity^{4–9}. It was demonstrated that decarbonylative metallation of 4-methyl-2,6-diformylphenol by $\text{Ru}(\text{PPh}_3)_3\text{Cl}_2$ in the presence of primary aromatic amines ($\text{RC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2$) affords organometallics of the type $\text{Ru}(\text{RL}^1)(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{CO})\text{Cl}$ (**1**), incorporating a four-membered chelate ring juxtaposed to a hydrogen bonded iminium-phenolato ring^{10–12}. The reactivity of these compounds is being investigated in this laboratory. While alkynes and isonitriles

have been found to promote metallacycle expansion^{5–7,13,14}, bidentate monoanionic σ -donor reagents such as acetate, nitrite, nitrate, xanthate and pyridine-2-thiolate undergo four-membered chelation^{15–18}. Electroneutral α -diimine ligands such as bipyridine, phenanthroline, 2-(2-pyridyl)-benzthiazole furnish potentially fluorescent five-membered ruthenium organometallics¹⁹.

Herein we explore for the first time, the reactivity of the

four-membered ruthenium organometallics, **1**, towards long chain carboxylate as well as dicarboxylate. The reaction of **1** with sodium palmitate and disodium terephthalate has indeed afforded a new family of ruthenium palmitate and terephthalate bridged dimeric ruthenium organometallics respectively. Their synthesis and properties are described and rationalized in this work.

Results and discussion

Synthesis :

Upon treating **1** in dichloromethane-acetone solution with a five-fold excess of aqueous NaPm, a yellow solution

was afforded from which $\text{Ru}(\text{RL}^2)(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{CO})(\text{Pm})$, **2**, was obtained in excellent yield, which is low melting wax like solid. Whereas treatment with Na_2Tp in 2 : 1 ratio in the same solvent furnished the yellow coloured novel binuclear ruthenium organometallics, $[\text{Ru}(\text{RL}^2)(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{CO})]_2(\text{Tp})$, **3**. The synthetic reaction is given in eq. (1) and eq. (2).

The R groups utilized in the present work are Me and Cl. Specific compounds will be identified by putting R in parenthesis. Thus **2**(Me) and **3**(Me) stand for Ru(MeL²)(PPh₃)₂(CO)(Pm) and [Ru(MeL²)(PPh₃)₂(CO)]₂(Tp) respectively. Carboxyl chelated ruthenium complexes are well documented in literature^{20–22}. But organoruthenium species incorporating palmitate chelation and also terephthalate bridged binuclear ruthenium organometallics appear to be unprecedented.

3

The organometallics of type **2** and **3** are non-electrolytic in solution and are uniformly diamagnetic consistent with the metal oxidation state of +2.

Chelation and prototropic shift :

The conversions **1** → **2** and **1** → **3** are attended with a prototropic shift within the salicylidimine function. In **1** the metal is coordinated to phenolato oxygen and the Schiff base function occurs in the zwitterionic iminium-phenolato tautomeric form **4**. Chelation of palmitate/terephthalate is attended with cleavage of the Ru–O(phenolato) bond and the Schiff base fragment becomes an imine-phenol **5**. This

4

5

is fully consistent with the spectroscopic data. Thus the C=N stretching frequency in **2** and **3** is significantly lower (~1600 cm⁻¹) than that in **1** (~1620 cm⁻¹) as expected^{23,24}. Also the aldimine CH resonance in ¹H NMR in both **2** and **3** occurs at a lower field viz. ~ 8.0 ppm as compared to ~ 7.5 ppm in **1**. The O–H resonance in both types of complexes occurs as a relatively sharp signal near 12.5 ppm having a half-height width of ~30 Hz. In contrast the iminium N–H resonance in **1** is broad (width, ~150 Hz) evidently due to the quadrupole moment of the nitrogen atom¹⁰

Spectroscopic characterization :

In dichloromethane solution the complexes display two allowed absorption bands in the region 400–415 nm and 335–340 nm, the latter being more intense. The absence of the allowed band near 500 nm due to the *t*_{2g} → π* (azomethine) charge transfer transition which is diagnostic of the coordinated iminium-phenolato function⁷, evidently proves that in **2** and **3** the function becomes imine-phenol. In IR, the C=O stretch in **2** and **3** occurs in the region 1930–1940 cm⁻¹, which is slightly higher than the precursor complex **1**¹⁰. Selected UV-vis and IR spectral data are given in Table 1.

Table 1. UV-vis and IR spectral data

Complexes	UV-vis data ^a	IR data ^c	
	$\lambda_{\text{max}}(\text{nm})(\epsilon^b, \text{M}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1})$	$\nu_{\text{C=O}} (\text{cm}^{-1})$	$\nu_{\text{C=N}} (\text{cm}^{-1})$
2 (Me)	336 (11530), 405 (2330)	1932	1593
2 (Cl)	340 (15370), 410 (2780)	1930	1606
3 (Me)	337 (23160), 403 (5560)	1934	1591
3 (Cl)	340 (20070), 411 (4070)	1938	1605

^aSolvent is dichloromethane. ^bExtinction coefficient. ^cIn KBr disc.

In ¹H NMR the 3-H and 4-Me protons appear as sharp singlets near 6.20 and 2.00 ppm. These protons as well as the 5-H proton are subject to shielding by phosphine phenyl ring^{10,15,25}. The 5-H signal is observed near 6.8 ppm in **3** but in **2** it merges with the complex aromatic multiplet due to PPh₃ and C₆H₄R protons. Palmitate CH₂-protons appear as a multiplet in the region 1.20–1.35 ppm and methyl protons appear as a sharp signal near 1.75 ppm. There is a complex multiplet of the aromatic protons in **2** and **3**, which appear in the region 6.90–7.63 and 7.15–7.41 ppm respectively. Selected data are given in Table 2.

Table 2. ¹H NMR spectral data in CDCl₃

Complexes	δ, ppm^a					
	-OH	4-Me	3-H	5-H	7-H	13-Me
2 (Me)	12.65	2.01	6.16	–	8.04	2.38
2 (Cl)	12.37	1.98	6.17	–	8.01	–
3 (Me)	12.71	2.17	6.23	6.83	8.08	2.39
3 (Cl)	12.44	2.02	6.24	6.83	8.06	–

^aAll signals are singlets.

The formation of **3**(Me) and **3**(Cl) has been also confirmed by electrospray mass spectra. Molecular ion peaks, at *m/z* 1963 (formula weight, 1960.84) and 1919 (formula weight, 1920.00) are exhibited for **3**(Me) and **3**(Cl) respectively.

Electrochemistry : metal oxidation :

In dichloromethane solution, **2** displays a well-defined quasireversible one-electron cyclic voltammetric response (Fig. 1) near 0.6 V versus SCE corresponding to the Ru^{III}/Ru^{II} couple. The reduction potentials are systematically lower than those of the type **1** precursors¹⁰ by ~100 mV indicating better stabilization of the trivalent state in **2** compared with **1**. In contrast, **3** displays two successive quasireversible one-electron oxidation processes at half-wave potentials ($E_{1/2}$) near 0.6 V and 0.9 V vs SCE (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammograms of **2**(Me) (-----) and **3**(Me) (–) in dichloromethane solution.

These oxidation processes are assigned as the stepwise oxidations of the two ruthenium(II) centres²⁶, i.e. two successive Ru^{III}/Ru^{II} couples separated by 300 mV due to a strong electronic interaction across the terephthalate bridge. In all cases the $E_{1/2}$ values of the chloride substituent shift marginally to higher potentials following the Hammett order. The $E_{1/2}$ values of **2** and **3** are listed in Table 3.

Table 3. Cyclic voltammetric reduction potentials^a

Complexes	M ^{III} -M ^{II}	n^{lel}
	$E_{1/2}^a$, V(ΔE_p , mV)	
2 (Me)	0.57 (130)	1.02
2 (Cl)	0.61 (141)	1.04
3 (Me)	0.88 (210), 0.60 (160)	1.07
3 (Cl)	0.92 (192), 0.62 (150)	0.98

^aConditions solvent, dichloromethane; supporting electrolyte, TEAP (0.1 M); working electrode, platinum; reference electrode, SCE solute concentration, $\sim 10^{-3}$ M; $E_{1/2} = 0.5(E_{pa} + E_{pc})$ at scan rate 50 mV s^{-1} , where E_{pa} and E_{pc} are the anodic and cathodic peak potentials, respectively, $\Delta E_p = E_{pa} - E_{pc}$. $n^{lel} = Q/Q'$ where Q is the observed coulomb count and Q' is the calculated coulomb count for one-electron transfer.

Constant potential coulometric oxidation of **2** and **3** at 0.8 V afforded a coulomb count corresponding to a one-electron transfer (Table 3). The trivalent organometallics **2**⁺ and mixed valent **3**⁺ generated coulometrically have been examined in solution. Their cyclic voltammograms (initial scan cathodic) are virtually superimposable on those of **2** and **3** (initial scan anodic) respectively. This proves that **2**⁺ and **3**⁺ retains the gross structure of **2** and **3**. The solutions are EPR-active by quick frozen into the glassy state (dichloromethane/toluene, 77 K), giving rise to well-resolved rhombic spectra that are consistent with a low-spin $4d^5$ configuration in non-axial geometry^{27,28}.

In case of **3**⁺ formation of mixed valent ruthenium organometallics is clearly evident, from the comparison of g -values with the monomeric Ru^{III} species and several other Ru^{II,III} complexes reported earlier^{29,30}. A representative EPR spectrum (Fig. 2) and g -values (Table 4) are given here.

Fig. 2. X-band EPR spectrum of electrogenerated **3**(Me)⁺ in dichloromethane-toluene glass at 77 K. Instrument settings: power, 30 dB; modulation, 100 KHz; sweep centre, 3200 G.

Table 4. EPR spectroscopic data of **2**⁺ and **3**⁺

Complexes	EPR g Values		
	g_1	g_2	g_3
2 (Me) ⁺	2.579	2.156	1.856
2 (Cl) ⁺	2.573	2.151	1.884
3 (Me) ⁺	2.552	2.144	1.821
3 (Cl) ⁺	2.543	2.140	1.821

Conclusion :

It is demonstrated that **1** undergoes facile substitution of halide by palmitate furnishing a new family of ruthenium

organometallics of type **2** which is low melting solid than sodium palmitate; this can be attributed to the substantial covalent character in the former compound. With terephthalate it produces dimeric ruthenium organometallics of type **3**. The **1** → **2/3** conversions are attended with cleavage of the Ru–O and Ru–Cl bonds, (O,O) chelation of palmitate/terephthalate, iminium-phenolato → imine-phenol tautomerization. In solution, **2** and **3** are electrooxidizable to their Ru^{III} analogue **2**⁺ and mixed valent Ru^{II,III} analogue **3**⁺ respectively.

Experimental

Materials :

The compounds Ru(PPh₃)₃Cl₂³¹ and Ru(RL¹)(PPh₃)₂(CO)Cl¹⁰ were prepared by reported methods, palmitic acid and terephthalic acid were obtained from Merck. The purification of dichloromethane for electro-chemical work was done as described before^{27,32}. All other chemicals and solvents were of analytical grade and were used as received.

Physical measurements :

Electronic and IR spectra were recorded on Shimadzu UV-1601 PC spectrophotometer and Nicolet Magna IR series II spectrometer respectively. The Electrospray mass spectrum was recorded on a Finnigan LCQ ADVANTAGE mass spectrometer. ¹H NMR spectra were obtained using a Bruker 300 MHz FT NMR spectrometer. The numbering scheme used for ¹H NMR is the same as in drawing I. Spin-spin structures are abbreviated as : s, singlet; d, doublet; t, triplet; m, multiplet. Microanalyses (C, H, N) were done by using a Perkin-Elmer 240C elemental analyzer. Solution electrical conductivity was measured in acetone with a Phillips PR 9500 bridge using a platinized electrode (cell constant of 1.05). The magnetic behaviour of the complexes was examined by a PAR 155 vibrating sample magnetometer. The cyclic voltammetric (scan rate 50 mV s⁻¹) measurements were performed at a platinum electrode under a nitrogen atmosphere in dichloromethane solution using a model 620A electrochemical analyzer of CH instrument. The supporting electrolyte was tetraethylammonium perchlorate and potentials are referenced to the saturated calomel electrode (SCE).

Preparation of sodium palmitate (NaPm) and disodium terephthalate (Na₂Tp) salts :

In a 250 ml beaker 0.7 g (17.5 mmol) NaOH was taken. Then 100 ml of distilled water was added to it. The solution was then stirred for 10 min and to this stirred solution 4 g (15.6 mmol) of palmitic acid was added slowly. The mixture was then stirred for 1 h with heating and then the

solvent was evaporated on water bath to deposit the salt. It was then filtered by washing with cold water and dried in vacuo, yield 3.1 g (71%).

Using 2.2 g (55 mmol) of NaOH and 4 g (24 mmol) of terephthalic acid following the same procedure disodium salt of terephthalic acid was obtained.

Synthesis of the complexes :

The ruthenium palmitates, Ru(RL²)(PPh₃)₂(CO)(Pm) and terephthalate bridged binuclear ruthenium organometallics, [Ru(RL²)(PPh₃)₂(CO)]₂(Tp) were synthesized in excellent yields by reacting Ru(RL¹)(PPh₃)₂(CO)Cl with sodium palmitate (NaPm) in 1 : 5 and with disodium terephthalate (Na₂Tp) in 2 : 1 molar ratio respectively. Details are given below for two representative cases.

Ru(MeL²)(PPh₃)₂(CO)(Pm) :

To a vigorously stirred violet solution of Ru(MeL¹)(PPh₃)₂(CO)Cl (100 mg, 0.109 mmol) in a mixture of dichloromethane (20 ml) and acetone (40 ml) was added dropwise an aqueous solution of NaPm (152 mg, 0.546 mmol). The mixture was stirred for two hours when the original violet color became clear yellow. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure. Then isolated by filtration, washed repeatedly with hot water, and dried in vacuo, yield 85% (Found : C, 72.10; H, 6.71; N, 1.21. Calcd. for C₆₈H₇₅NO₄P₂Ru : C, 72.06; H, 6.67; N, 1.24%).

Ru(CiL²)(PPh₃)₂(CO)(Pm) :

Ru(CiL¹)(PPh₃)₂(CO)Cl (100 mg, 0.107 mmol) and NaPm (149 mg, 0.535 mmol) were employed, yield 83% (Found : C, 69.70; H, 6.33; N, 1.25. Calcd. for C₆₇H₇₂NO₄P₂ClRu : C, 69.75; H, 6.29; N, 1.21%).

[Ru(MeL²)(PPh₃)₂(CO)]₂(Tp) :

To a vigorously stirred violet solution of Ru(MeL¹)(PPh₃)₂(CO)Cl (100 mg, 0.109 mmol) in a mixture of dichloromethane (20 ml) and acetone (40 ml) was added dropwise an aqueous solution of Na₂Tp (11 mg, 0.052 mmol). The mixture was stirred for two hours when the original violet color became clear yellow. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure. Then isolated by filtration, washed repeatedly with cold water, and dried in vacuo, yield 82% (Found : C, 70.11; H, 4.87; N, 1.42. Calcd. for C₁₁₂H₉₂N₂O₈P₄Ru₂ : C, 70.06; H, 4.83; N, 1.46%).

[Ru(CiL²)(PPh₃)₂(CO)]₂(Tp) :

Ru(CiL¹)(PPh₃)₂(CO)Cl (100 mg, 0.107 mmol) and Na₂Tp (11 mg, 0.052 mmol) were used, yield 79% (Found : C, 67.28; H, 4.47; N, 1.46. Calcd. for C₁₁₀H₈₆N₂O₈P₄Cl₂Ru₂ : C, 67.32; H, 4.42; N, 1.43%).

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